

2a-c

- 2a ; R = C₂H₅ (C₁₃H₁₁N₂S₂)
 2b ; R = CH₃-C₆H₅ (C₁₇H₁₅N₂S₂)
 2c ; R = C₆H₄-CH₃-p (C₁₇H₁₅N₂S₂)

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of some Pyrimidyl and Thiazolyl Substituted Thioureas as Potential Fungicides and Nematicides

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A survey of literature reveals that some work has been done on thioureas¹ but not much has been done on the synthesis and spectral studies of substituted pyrimidyl- and thiazolyl thioureas. The present communication reports the synthesis, structure determination and screening of the pyrimidyl-thioureas (1a-f) and thiazolylthioureas (2a-c) against the fungi *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Pythium aphanidermatum* and the nematodes *Meloidogyne javanica* and *Anguina tritici*.

1a-f

- 1a ; R = C₂H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = H (C₇H₁₀N₂S)
 1b ; R = CH₃-C₆H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = H (C₁₂H₁₃N₂S)
 1c ; R = C₆H₄-CH₃-p, R₁ = H, R₂ = H (C₁₃H₁₂N₂S)
 1d ; R = C₂H₅, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₃ (C₈H₁₂N₂OS)
 1e ; R = CH₃-C₆H₅, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₃ (C₁₃H₁₄N₂OS)
 1f ; R = C₆H₄-CH₃-p, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₃ (C₁₃H₁₄N₂OS)

Experimental

The chemicals used were of G.R. (E. Merck or Sarabhai M) grade. Ethyl, benzyl and *p*-tolyl-isothiocyanates were prepared by the reported method². Six pyrimidylthioureas (1a-f) and three thiazolylthioureas (2a-c) were prepared as follows. To a solution of 2-aminopyrimidine or 2-aminothiazole (0.5 mol) in a minimum quantity of ethanol or to a solution of 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine (0.5 mol) in a minimum quantity of 50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture, an equivalent amount of the isothiocyanate (ethyl/benzyl/*p*-tolyl) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 6-8 h, cooled and the resulting crystals of the substituted-thioureas were washed with ethanol, air-dried and recrystallised from ethanol. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc, elemental analysis and molecular weight determination by cryoscopic method.

Melting point was determined by a Genson melting point apparatus. Electronic spectra (ethanol) were determined on a Beckman DU 20 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (nujol or KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on Varian A-60D/Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument using TMS as internal standard.

The compounds were screened for their anti-fungal activity³ and nematicidal activity⁴ as reported earlier.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis (C, H, N and S) were found satisfactory for all the compounds. The ir spectra showed bands at 3 100-3 400 (NH), 1 630-1 650 (NH+C=C+C=N), 1 510-1 560 (NH+C=S+NCS), 1 205-1 280 (C=S+NCS), 1 000-1 070 (NCN+C=S+C=N) and 820-840 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C cyclic for compounds 2a-c) suggesting the most probable structures for these substituted thioureas. The compounds exhibited three intense bands at 201-214, 231-267 and 270-307 nm corresponding⁵ to high energy π-π* transition of substituted pyrimidyl/thiazolyl group, thiocarbonyl π→π* transition and pyrimidyl/thiazolyl π→π* transition plus n→π* transition due to non-bonded electrons of the ring nitrogen respectively. The nmr spectra of compounds 1a, e and 2b were taken as representative case: 1a m.p. 120°, δ 1.50-1.70 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH₃), 2.69 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH₂), 8.70-8.80 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, 2×NH); 1b m.p. 181°; 1c m.p. 145°; 1d m.p. 215°; 1e m.p. 190°, δ 3.12

(2H, s, CH₂), 7.50–7.70 (6H, m, ArH), 8.80–8.90 (2×NH); **1f** m.p. 198°; **2a** m.p. 134°; **2b** m.p. 125°, δ 3.25 (2H, s, CH₂–Ar), 7.40–7.80 (10H, m, ArH); **2c** m.p. 120°.

Biological activities : The toxicity data (EC₅₀ μg ml⁻¹) reveal that compounds **1f** (0.79), **2a** (0.22) and **2c** (0.25) were highly toxic against *R. solani* and compounds **1d** (0.42), **1e** (0.44), **1f** (0.71), **2b** (0.60) and **2c** (0.69) were highly toxic against *P. aphanidermatum* having EC₅₀ < 10 μg ml⁻¹. Compounds **2a–c** were found to be highly toxic against *M. javanica* whereas only **2c** was found to be highly toxic against *A. tritici* having 100% mortality even at 1 : 20 dilution. The other compounds were moderately toxic against these nematodes.

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